

A Comprehensive Report: Plant Design for the Production of Ammonia

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Ammonia is a chemical consisting of one atom of nitrogen and three atoms of hydrogen. It is designated in chemical notation as NH₃. This report comprehensively describes ammonia, its physical and chemical properties along with the methods that are available for its production. This report further explains about the important aspects of the manufacturing process and presents them in detail along with the relevant equations and flow diagrams. This report incorporates a detailed material and energy balance of the selected process and provides a list of the size of the equipment's in the flow diagram according to the capacity. The total capacity of the design shown in this report for the production of ammonia is 200 tonnes per day.

Keywords: AMMONIA, FLOW-DIAGRAMS, PRODUCTION, ENERGY BALANCE, MATERIAL

Introduction

Ammonia is a chemical consisting of one atom of nitrogen and three atoms of hydrogen. It is designated in chemical notation as NH₃.

Ammonia is extremely soluble in water and is frequently used as a water solution called aqua ammonia. Ammonia chemically combines with water to form ammonium hydroxide. Household ammonia is a diluted water solution containing 5 to 10 percent ammonia. On the other hand,

anhydrous ammonia is essentially pure (over 99 percent) ammonia. "Anhydrous" is a Greek word meaning "without water;" therefore, anhydrous ammonia is the ammonia without water.

Refrigerant grade anhydrous ammonia is a clear, colourless liquid or gas, free from visible impurities. It is at least 99.95 percent pure ammonia. Water cannot have a content above 33 parts per million (ppm) and oil cannot have a content above 2 ppm. Preserving the purity of the ammonia is essential to ensure proper function of the refrigeration system.

Physical Properties

Anhydrous ammonia is a clear liquid that boils at a temperature of -28°F . In refrigeration systems, the liquid is stored in closed containers under pressure. When the pressure is released, the liquid evaporates rapidly, generally forming an invisible vapour or gas. The rapid evaporation causes the temperature of the liquid to drop until it reaches the normal boiling point of -28°F , a similar effect occurs when water evaporates off the skin, thus cooling it. This is why ammonia is used in refrigeration systems.

Liquid anhydrous ammonia weighs less than water. About eight gallons of ammonia weighs the same as five gallon of water

Liquid and gas ammonia expand and contract with changes in pressure and temperature. For example, if liquid anhydrous ammonia is in a partially filled, closed container it is heated from 0°F to 68°F , the volume of the liquid will increase by about 10 percent. If the tank is 90 percent full at 0°F , it will become 99 percent full at 68°F . At the same time, the pressure in the container will increase from 16 pounds per square inch (psi) to 110 psi.

Liquid ammonia will expand by 850 times when evaporating:

Anhydrous ammonia gas is considerably lighter than air and will rise in dry air. However, because of ammonias tremendous affinity for water, it reacts immediately with the humidity in the air and may remain close to the ground.

The odour threshold for ammonia is between 5 - 50 parts per million (ppm) of air. The permissible exposure limit (PEL) is 50 ppm averaged over an 8 hour shift. It is recommended that if an employee can smell it they ought to back off and determine if they need to be using respiratory protection.

Chemical Properties

Ammonia, especially in the presence of moisture, reacts with and corrodes copper, zinc, and many alloys. Only iron, steel, certain rubbers and plastics, and specific nonferrous alloys resistant to ammonia should be used for fabrications of anhydrous ammonia containers, fittings, and piping.

Ammonia will combine with mercury to form a fulminate which is an unstable explosive compound.

Anhydrous ammonia is classified by the Department of Transportation as non-flammable. However, ammonia vapour in high concentrations (16 to 25 percent by weight in air) will burn. It is unlikely that such concentrations will occur except in confined spaces or in the proximity of large spills. The fire hazard from ammonia is increased by the presence of oil or other combustible substances.

Anhydrous ammonia is an alkali.

Summary of properties:

Boiling Point	-28°F
Weight per gallon of liquid at -28°F	5.69 pounds
Weight per gallon of liquid at 60°F	5.15 pounds

Specific gravity of the liquid (water=1)	0.619
Specific gravity of the gas (air=1)	0.588
Flammable limits in air	16-25%
Ignition temperature	1204°F
Vapour pressure at 0°F	16 psi
Vapour pressure at 68°F	110 psi
Vapour pressure at 100°F	198 psi
One cubic foot of liquid at 60°F expands to	850 cubic foot of gas

- Ammonia Molecular weight : 17.03 g/mol
- Ammonia Melting point : -78oC
- Ammonia Latent heat of fusion (1,013 bar, at triple point) : 331.37 kJ/kg
- Ammonia Liquid Density (1.013 bar at boiling point) : 682 kg/m³ (250 K : 669 kg/m³)(300 K : 600 kg/m³) (400 K : 346 kg/m³)
- Ammonia Liquid Specific Heat Capacity (cp) (250 K : 4.52 kJ/kg.K) (300 K : 4.75kJ/kg.K) (400 K : 6.91 kJ/kg.K)
- Ammonia Liquid/gas equivalent (1.013 bar and 15oC (59oF)) : 947 vol/vol
- Ammonia Liquid Dynamic Viscosity (250K : 245 106 Ns/m²) (300K : 141 106 Ns/m²)(400K : 38 106 Ns/m²)
- Ammonia Liquid Thermal Conductivity (250 K : 592 106 kW/m.K) (300 K : 477 106kW/m.K) (400 K : 207 106 kW/m.K)
- Ammonia Boiling point (1.013 bar) : -33.5oC
- Ammonia Latent heat of vaporization (1.013 bar at boiling point) : 1371.2 kJ/kg
- Ammonia Vapour pressure (at 21oC or 70oF) : 8.88 bar
- Ammonia Critical point - Critical temperature : 132.4oC - Critical pressure : 112.8 bar
- Ammonia Gas Density (1.013 bar at boiling point) : 0.86 kg/m³
- Ammonia Gas Density (1.013 bar and 15oC (59oF)) : 0.73 kg/m³
- Ammonia Gas Compressibility Factor (Z) (the ratio of the actual volume of the gas to the volume determined according to the perfect gas law) (1.013 bar and 15oC (59oF)) : 0.9929
- Ammonia Gas Specific Gravity (air = 1) (1.013 bar and 21oC (70oF)) : 0.597
- Ammonia Gas Specific volume (1.013 bar and 21oC (70oF)) : 1.411 m³/kg
- Ammonia Gas Specific Heat Capacity at constant pressure (cp) (1.013 bar and 15oC (59oF)) : 0.037 kJ/(mol.K)

- Ammonia Gas Specific Heat Capacity at constant volume (cv) (1.013 bar and 15oC (59oF)) : 0.028 kJ/(mol.K)
- Ammonia Gas Ratio of Specific Heats (Gamma: cp/cv) (1.013 bar and 15oC (59oF)) : 1.309623
- Ammonia Gas Dynamic Viscosity (1.013 bar and 0oC (32oF)) : 0.000098 Poise
- Ammonia Gas Thermal conductivity (1.013 bar and 0oC (32oF)) : 22.19 mW/(m.K)
- Ammonia Gas Solubility in water (1.013 bar and 0oC (32oF)) : 862 vol/vol
- Ammonia Gas Auto ignition temperature : 630oC

Methodology: Process Flow Diagram

Material Balance

Natural gas composition (as supplied by ONGC):

Component	Vol %
CH ₄	89.96
C ₂ H ₆	4.09
C ₃ H ₈	2.3
i-C ₄ H ₁₀	0.46
n-C ₄ H ₁₀	0.6
i-C ₅ H ₁₂	0.2
n-C ₅ H ₁₂	0.2
CO ₂	0.35
N ₂	1.84

Sulphur content : 5 ppm

(Data taken from IFFCO Kalol plant manual)

Calculating from above data:

Mole fraction of carbon, x_C: 0.219

Mole fraction of hydrogen, x_H: 0.781

Primary Reformer

Main reaction of primary reformer is

Inlet temperature of primary reformer: 500°C

Outlet temperature of primary reformer: 800°C

Let flow rate of inlet stream: F₁ (mol/s)

Composition of primary reformer outlet:

XH ₂	0.337
XCO ₂	0.051
XH ₂ O	0.489
XCO	0.087
XCH ₄	0.0357

$$\text{Steam added} = 3 \times x_C \times F_1 = 0.657F_0$$

Let outlet flow rate = F₂ mol/s

Balancing carbon at inlet and outlet of primary reformer

$$0.219F_1 = (0.087 + 0.051 + 0.0357)$$

$$F_2 \cdot 0.219F_1 = 0.1737F_2$$

$$F_2 = 1.261 \times F_1 \quad \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Secondary Reformer

Inlet temperature: 800°C

Reactions taking place here are:

Air is added here so that complete conversion of CH₄ takes place

Let air added = A mol/s

So,

$$0.21 \times A = 2 \times x_{CH_4} \times F_2$$

$$A = 0.34 F_2 = 0.429F_1 \quad \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Composition at secondary reformer outlet

XH ₂	0.365
XCO ₂	0.055
XN ₂	0.1446
XCO	0.0735
XCH ₄	0.0012
Xinert	0.0007
Xsteam	0.36

Balancing carbon at inlet and outlet of secondary reformer:

$$(0.087+0.051+0.0357) F_2 = (0.0735+0.055+0.0012) F_3$$

$$F_3 = 1.339 \times F_2 = 1.689 \times F_1 \quad \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

High Temperature Shift Converter

Inlet temperature: 400°C

Outlet composition of HTSC:

XH ₂	0.418
XCO ₂	0.108
XN ₂	0.145
XCO	0.02
XCH ₄	0.0012
Xinert	0.0007
Xsteam	0.3

Balancing carbon:

$$0.1297 F_3 = (0.02+.108+.0012) F_4$$

$$F_4 = 1.004F_3 = 1.689F_1 \quad \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Low Temperature Shift Converter

Inlet temperature: 200°C

Outlet composition of LTSC:

XH ₂	0.436
XCO ₂	0.126
XN ₂	0.145
XCO	0.002
XCH ₄	0.0012
Xinert	0.0012
Xsteam	0.289

Balancing carbon,

We get $F_5 = F_4 = 1.689F_1$ (5)

Condenser

Outlet from LTSC goes to condenser, where steam gets condensed out and rest of the gases go to CO₂ absorber section.

At inlet of condenser:

XH ₂	0.436	0.736F ₁
XCO ₂	0.126	0.213 F ₁
XN ₂	0.145	0.245 F ₁
XCO	0.002	0.003 F ₁
XCH ₄	0.0012	0.0012 F ₁
Xinert	0.0012	0.0012 F ₁
Xsteam	0.289	0.488 F ₁

Synthesis Loop

Compositions: (mole fraction)

Component	Purge (P _g)	Recycle (R)	At convertor inlet, (F _{ci})
H ₂	0.721	0.618	0.645
N ₂	0.0898	0.205	0.215
NH ₃	0.0955	0.0257	0.019
Inerts	0.0932	0.151	0.1199

Applying mass balance for completer loop,

$$M(x_{\text{inert}})M = P_g(x_{\text{inert}})P_g$$

$$M(x_{\text{N}_2})M = P_g(x_{\text{N}_2})P_g + \frac{1}{2}(P_g(x_{\text{NH}_3})P_g + 136.2)$$

$$M(x_{\text{H}_2})M = P_g(x_{\text{H}_2})P_g + \frac{3}{2}(P_g(x_{\text{NH}_3})P_g + 136.2)$$

Adding all these,

$$M = 1.095P_g + 272.4 \quad \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

Also at separator,

$$F_{co} = P_g + R + 136.2 \quad \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

At recycle point,

$$F_{ci} = M + R \quad \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

Taking 14% conversion per pass for the reactor at 200 atm pressure and 500°C,

$$F_{co} = F_{ci} (x_{N2})_{F_{ci}} \times 0.86 + F_{ci} (x_{H2})_{F_{ci}} \times 0.86 + F_{ci} (x_{NH3})_{F_{ci}} + F_{ci} (x_{N2})_{F_{ci}} \times 0.28 + F_{ci} (x_{inert})_{F_{ci}}$$

On solving,

$$F_{co} = 0.9387 \times F_{ci} \quad \dots\dots\dots (9)$$

Also at recycle,

$$R(x_{NH3})_R = F_{ci}(x_{NH3})_{F_{ci}}$$

$$F_{ci} = 1.35 \times R \quad \dots\dots\dots (10)$$

Solving eqs. (6), (7), (8), (9) and (10)

Stream	Flow rate (Mol/s)
R	2136.12
M	747.64
F _{ci}	2883.76
P _g	434.18
F _{co}	2706.98

Make up gas to synthesis loop comes from methanator.

Methanator

Outlet composition of this is same as that at inlet of synthesis loop.

Components	Mole fraction	Flow rate (Mol/s)
H ₂	0.737	552.88
N ₂	0.249	186.54
CH ₄	0.007	5.15
Inert (CO, CO ₂ , & Ar)	0.004	3
Steam	0.003	2.25

Inlet flow rate for methanator can be calculated using inlet composition for methanator and balancing flow rate of nitrogen (as nitrogen remains unaffected in methanator).

Inlet flow rate and composition of methanator are:

Components	Mole fraction	Flow rate (Mol/s)
H ₂	0.745	562.54
N ₂	0.247	186.54
CH ₄	0.002	1.51
Inert	0.001	0.75
CO	0.004	3.02
CO ₂	0.001	0.75

CO₂ Absorber

In CO₂ absorber, only Carbon dioxide is absorbed and rest of the gases remain unaffected. Inlet and outlet compositions for CO₂ absorber,

Components	Inlet mole fraction	Outlet mole fraction	Outlet flow rate (Mol/s)
H ₂	0.687	0.745	562.54
N ₂	0.228	0.247	186.54
CH ₄	0.002	0.002	1.51
Inert	0.004	0.001	0.75
CO	0.078	0.004	3.02
CO ₂	0.001	0.001	0.75

Let inlet flow rate: Fa

Balancing hydrogen in CO₂ absorber,

$$Fa \times 0.687 = 562.64$$

$$Fa = 818.98 \text{ mol/s}$$

$$\text{CO}_2 \text{ removed in CO}_2 \text{ absorber} = 0.078 \times 818.98 - 0.75$$

$$= 63.13 \text{ mol/s}$$

Condensor

Steam formed in LTSC & HTSC is removed in this unit. Outlet for condenser is inlet for the absorber. As other gases do not get affected, so we can balance flow rate for any other gas.

X _{H2}	0.436	0.736F ₁
X _{CO2}	0.126	0.213 F ₁
X _{N2}	0.145	0.245 F ₁
X _{CO}	0.002	0.003 F ₁
X _{CH4}	0.0012	0.0012 F ₁
X _{inert}	0.0012	0.0012 F ₁
X _{steam}	0.289	0.488 F ₁

Equating flow of hydrogen

$$0.736 \times F_1 = 562.64$$

$$F_1 = 764.46 \text{ mol/s}$$

Using relations (1), (2), (3), (4) and (5)

$$F_2 = 963.98 \text{ mol/s}$$

$$F_3 = F_4 = F_5 = 1291.8 \text{ mol/s}$$

Air added in secondary reformer, A = 327.95 mol/s

Steam added in primary reformer = 502.25 mol/s

Energy Balance

Primary Reformer

Reactions taking place in primary reformer are:

Inlet temperature: 500°C

Outlet temperature: 800°C

$$H_{1073} = H_{298} + \int_{298}^{1073} \sum x_i \times C_{pi}$$

Thus,

Heat required by first reaction: Flow rate of methane $\times (\Delta H_{1073})_1$

$$= 1.87 \times 10^7 \text{ J/s}$$

Heat liberated by second reaction : Flow rate of carbon monoxide $\times (\Delta H_{1073})_2$

$$= 7.55 \times 10^5 \text{ J/s}$$

Enthalpy content of outlet stream:

$$\Sigma (F \cdot x \cdot C_p \cdot 1073) = 4.05 \times 10^7 \text{ J/s}$$

Enthalpy content of inlet stream:

$$\Sigma (F \cdot x \cdot C_p \cdot 773) = 3.81 \times 10^7 \text{ J/s}$$

Additional heat required,

$$4.05 \times 10^7 + 1.87 \times 10^7 - 7.55 \times 10^5 - 3.81 \times 10^7 \text{ J/s} = 2.03 \times 10^7 \text{ J/s}$$

Part of this heat is provided by the steam (at 30 atm)

Steam enthalpy = 2802.3 kJ/Kg = 50491.9 J/mol

Enthalpy content in steam = $2.53 \times 10^6 \text{ J/s}$

Rest of heating is done in convection zone of primary reformer using natural gas, Heat utility of

convection zone: $(2.03 - 0.253) \times 10^7 \text{ J/s}$

$$= 1.78 \times 10^7 \text{ J/s Calorific value}$$

$$\text{of natural gas} = 39383.2 \text{ kJ/m}^3$$

Amount of natural gas required

$$= 1.78 / 3.98 \text{ m}^3/\text{s} = 0.451 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$$

Secondary Reformer

Air added in secondary reformer = 327.95 mol/s

This is pre-heated to 800°C before being fed to secondary reformer. Heat required for heating air from 30°C to 800°C = $7 \times 10^6 \text{ J/s}$ Again natural gas is used for heating purpose,

Amount of natural gas required: $(7 \times 10^6) / (3.94 \times 10^7) = 0.178 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$

$\text{CH}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{CO} + 3\text{H}_2$	H = +ve
$\text{H}_2 + \frac{1}{2}\text{O}_2$	H_2O	H = - ve
$\text{CO} + \frac{1}{2}\text{O}_2$	CO_2	H = - ve

Heat required by reaction 1 at 1073 K = 0.34×10^7 J/s Heat liberated
 by reaction 2 at 1073 K = 0.49×10^7 J/s Heat liberated by reaction 3 at
 1073 K = 0.221×10^7 J/s Heat released due to the 3 reactions = 0.371
 $\times 10^7$ J/s

This heat increases temperature of outlet gas. Let this temperature be

$$T \quad 0.371 \times 10^7 = \Sigma (F .x .Cp.(T-1073))$$

solving ,

$$T = 1151.7 \text{ K}$$

Outlet temperature of secondary reformer = 1151.7 K

Heat Recovery Between Secondary Reformer & HTSC:

Effluent from secondary reformer is cooled to 693 K before being fed to HTSC. This heat is utilized for producing steam at 373 K and 1 atm.

$$\text{Steam produced: } \frac{\Delta H}{Cp\Delta T + \lambda s}$$

$$H = \text{heat recovered} = \Sigma (F .x .Cp.(1151-693)) = 2.22 \times 10^7 \text{ J/s}$$

$$\lambda_{\sigma} = 4.067 \times 10^7 \text{ J/kmol}$$

$$\text{Steam produced} = 0.547 \text{ kmol/s}$$

High Temperature Shift Converter:

Inlet temperature: 693 K

Heat released by the reaction: 0.133×10^7 J/s

Let outlet temperature of HTSC = T

$$\Delta H = \Sigma (F .x .Cp.(T-693))$$

$$T = 723.38 \text{ K}$$

Outlet temperature of HTSC = 723.38 K

Heat Recovery Between HTSC & LTSC:

Inlet temperature of LTSC = 473 K

$$\text{Heat removed} = \Sigma (F \cdot x \cdot C_p \cdot (723.38 - 473)) = 1.093 \times 10^7 \text{ J/s}$$

This heat is utilized for producing steam at 373 K and 1 atm.

Amount of steam produced:

$$\frac{\Delta H}{C_p \Delta T + \lambda s} = 269.33 \text{ mol/s}$$

Low Temperature Shift Convertor

Inlet temperature: 473 K

$$\text{Heat released by this reaction in LTSC} = 0.0422 \times 10^7 \text{ J/s}$$

Let outlet temperature of LTSC = T

$$\Sigma (F \cdot x \cdot C_p \cdot (T - 473)) = 0.0422 \times 10^7$$

$$T = 483 \text{ K}$$

Condenser

Exit stream from LTSC contains steam which is an unwanted load on absorber. In condenser, steam is condensed at 373 K (this is inlet temperature of absorber).

$$\text{Exit gases (other than steam) are also cooled from 483 to 373 K through a heat exchanger } \Delta H = \Sigma (F \cdot x \cdot C_p \cdot (483 - 373)) = 4.66 \times 10^7 \text{ J/s}$$

Methanator

Inlet temperature: 623 K

After absorber, gases are heated from 373 K to 623 K.

$$\text{Heat required} = \Sigma (F \cdot x \cdot C_p \cdot (623 - 373)) = 0.554 \times 10^7 \text{ J/s}$$

Steam is used for heating,

$$\text{Amount of steam utilized: } \frac{\Delta H}{\lambda s} = 133 \text{ mol/s}$$

Reaction taking place in methanator is:

$$\text{Heat released by this reaction in the methanator} = 5.4 \times 10^7 \text{ J/s}$$

Let outlet temperature = T

$$5.4 \times 10^7 = \Sigma (F \cdot x \cdot C_p \cdot (T-623))$$

$$T = 626K$$

Process Design

CO₂ Absorber

Gas flow rate at bottom $G_b = 818.98 \text{ mol/s} = 7.2 \text{ Kg/s}$

Gas flow rate at the top $G_t = 755.19 \text{ mol/s} = 4.43 \text{ Kg/s}$

$$Y_t = 0.001$$

$$Y_b = 0.0845$$

Properties

Gas density $\rho_g = 0.487 \text{ kg/m}^3$

Liquid density $\rho_l = 934.4 \text{ kg/m}^3$

Gas viscosity $\mu_g = 0.0175 \text{ cP}$

Liquid viscosity $\mu_l = 0.299 \text{ cP}$

Gas diffusivity $D_g = 1.65 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$

Liquid diffusivity $D_l = 1.96 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$

Gas heat capacity $C_{p_g} = 2.094 \text{ kJ/kg K}$

Liquid heat capacity $C_{p_l} = 4.145 \text{ kJ/kg K}$

Equilibrium data for absorption of CO₂ in MEA

X mol CO ₂ /mol inerts	Y mol CO ₂ /mol MEA sol
0.1	0
0.2	0.002
0.25	0.004
0.3	0.008
0.35	0.016
0.4	0.03

0.45	0.052
0.48	0.08
0.49	0.09

From Graph

$$(L_{in}/G_{in})_{min} = 0.217$$

$$(L_{in}/G_{in})_{actual} = 1.5 \times 0.217 = 0.3255$$

$$L_{in} = 0.325 \times 755.19$$

$$= 266.578 \text{ mol/s Top Section}$$

$$L_t = L_s (1 + X_t)$$

$$= 266.578 \text{ mol/s Bottom Section}$$

$$L_b = 266.578(1 + X_b)$$

$$= 361.4798 \text{ mol/s}$$

(as $X_b = 0.356$, from graph)

14.5 wt% MEA solution has molecular wt. = 20.08 kg/kmol

$$L_t = 5.35 \text{ kg/s}$$

$$L_b = 7.258 \text{ kg/s}$$

Thus, amount of MEA required for absorber = 5.35 kg/s with 0.1% of CO₂ coming from stripper.

Calculation of Column Diameter

Choosing 38 mm pall rings (metal)

Void fraction $\epsilon = 0.95$

Packing factor $F_p = 28$

Surface area $a = 128 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$

At the bottom $(L/G) \times (\rho_g/\rho_l) = 0.023$

At the top $(L/G) \times (\rho_g/\rho_l) = 0.0275$

Hence choosing the larger value of 0.027 (at top)

From Graph

$$G_f^2 F_p \psi \mu^{0.2} / (\rho_g \rho_l \gamma) = 0.01 \quad (\text{for } 200 \text{ N/m}^2 \text{ per m pressure})$$

Where

G_f = gas superficial velocity

F_p = packing factor = 28

ψ = correction factor for density = 1

μ = viscosity of liquid in cp = 0.299

ρ_g = density of gas = 0.487 kg/m³

ρ_l = density of liquid = 934.4 kg/m³

g = acceleration due to gravity

On substituting we obtain

$$G_f = 6.047 \text{ kg/m}^2 \text{ s}$$

Operating $G = 0.85 G_f$

$$= 5.1399 \text{ kg/m}^2 \text{ s} \quad A_c = G_t / G$$

$$A_c = 4.43 / 5.375 \quad A_c = 0.86 \text{ m}^2$$

$$D_i = 1.047 \text{ m}$$

Design dia = 1.05 m

Evaluation of tower height

$$Z = H_{OG} N_{OG}$$

$$H_{OG} = H_g + m(G_m/L_m)H_i$$

For ring type of packings

$$H_g = 0.017 \psi D^{1.24} Z^{0.33} S_{Cg}^{0.5} / (L f_1 f_2 f_3)^{0.5}$$

ψ = parameter for a given packing = 75

D = column diameter

S_{Cg} = Schmidt no for gas phase = 2.1778

L = liquid rate = 6.2 kg/m²s

$$f_1 = (\mu_l / \mu_w) = 0.8243$$

$$f_2 = (\rho_l / \rho_w) = 1.0885$$

$f_3 = (\sigma_w/\sigma_l) = 1.0611$ Substituting we

get $H_g = 0.822Z^{0.33}$

Liquid phase transfer unit

$H_l = (\phi C/3.28)Sc_l^{0.5}(Z/3.05)^{0.15}$

ϕ = correlation parameter for a given packing = 0.11 C = correlation

parameter for high gas flow rates = 0.5 Sc_l = Schmidt no for liquid

phase = .00163

Z = tower height

On substitution

$H_l = .000573Z^{0.15}$

m = slope of the equilibrium curve = 0.27

$L_m = 266.578$ mol/s

$G_m = 755.19$ mol/s

$H_{OG} = 0.822 \times Z^{0.33} + 0.00044 \times Z^{0.15}$

$N_{OG} = \int_{0.0845} \frac{dy}{y - y^*} - \frac{1}{2} \ln \left[\frac{(1 - y_b)}{(1 - y_t)} \right]$

y	y*	1/(y-y*)
.001	0	1000
.01	0.0005	105.283
.02	.001	52.63
.03	.0015	35.08
.04	.0025	26.26
.05	.004	21.74
.06	.006	18.5
.07	.009	16.4
.08	.0125	14.8
.084	.0145	14.38

$$N_{OG} = 4.78$$

$$Z = 3.93Z^{0.33} + 0.0021Z^{0.15}$$

By iterations,

$$Z = 7.70 \text{ m}$$

Height of bed in absorber = 7.7 m

$$\text{Pressure drop} = 1540 \text{ N/m}^2$$

Ammonia Converter

Let α fraction of feed goes to first bed and rest of $1-\alpha$ fraction mixes with effluent from 1st bed as quench gas to maintain temperature of gas at 500°C.

Also it is assumed that conversion in first bed is from 0 to 8 % , whereas in second converter conversion of 14 % is achieved.

$$\text{Heat liberated after first bed} = \alpha F \times 0.08 \times 0.215 \times 2 \times 46 \times 10^3 = 1582.4 \alpha F$$

After first Bed

H ₂	$(0.645 \times 0.92) \alpha F$	=	$0.5934 \alpha F$
N ₂	$(0.215 \times 0.92) \alpha F$	=	$0.1972 \alpha F$
NH ₃	$(2 \times 0.215 \times 0.08 + 0.02) \alpha F$	=	$0.0544 \alpha F$
Inert			$0.12 \alpha F$
			Total = $0.9656 \alpha F$

	Mole fraction	C _p (J/mol-K)
H ₂	0.614	29.572
N ₂	0.205	31.258
NH ₃	0.056	50.431
Inert	0.1242	20.796

$$\text{For the gas mixture, } C_p = 30.66 \text{ J/mol-K } 0.9656 \alpha F \times C_p \times \Delta T = 1582.4 \alpha F \Delta T = 53C$$

$$(T_1)_{out} = 480 + 53 = 533^\circ\text{C}$$

$$0.9656 \alpha F \times C_p \times 806 + (1 - \alpha) F \times C_p \times 626 = F(0.9656 \alpha + 1 - \alpha) C_p \times 753$$

$$\alpha = 0.71$$

2nd bed inlet:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{H}_2 & 0.5934 \times \alpha F + (1 - \alpha) F \times 0.645 = 0.608 F \\ \text{N}_2 & 0.1978 \times \alpha F + (1 - \alpha) F \times 0.215 = 0.208 F \\ \text{NH}_3 & 0.0544 \times \alpha F + (1 - \alpha) F \times 0.02 = 0.0444 F \\ \text{Inert} & 0.12 F = 0.12 F \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Flow rate} = 0.9752$$

	<u>Inlet mole fraction</u>
H ₂	0.623
N ₂	0.208
NH ₃	0.045
Inert	0.0123

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Heat liberated} & = [(F \text{ NH}_3)_{\text{out}} - (F \text{ NH}_3)_{\text{in}}] \times 46 \times 10^3 \\ & = (2706.98 \times 0.087 - 0.0444 \times 2883.76) \times 46 \times 10^3 \\ & = 4162.54 \times 10^3 \text{ J/s} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Out flow rate} = 2706.98 \text{ mol/s}$$

$$C_p = 30.5 \text{ J/mol-K}$$

$$2706.98 \times 30.5 \times \Delta T = 4162.54 \times 10^3$$

$$\Delta T = 50.4 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

$$\text{Final Temp} = 530.4 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

Heat Exchanger

$$0.71 \times F \times (753 - 626) = 2706.98 \times (803.5 - T)$$

$$812.87 - T = (0.71 \times 2883.76 \times 127) / 2706.98$$

$$= 707.44 \text{ K}$$

Volume of catalyst bed

$$V_1 \times C_{A0} / F_{A0} = \tau$$

$$\text{Space velocity} = 15000 \text{ hr}^{-1} \text{ (at standard conditions)}$$

$$\text{Space time} = 0.0747 \text{ s}$$

$$\text{Space time at operating condition} = (\Gamma / C_{A0}) \times C'_{A0}$$

$$C_{A0} = (1 \times 0.215) / (0.0821 \times 273)$$

$$= 9.6 \text{ mol/m}^3$$

$$C'_{A0} = (200 \times 0.215) / (0.0821 \times 773)$$

$$= 678.4 \text{ mol/m}^3$$

$$\text{Space time at operating conditions} = 0.0747 \times 678.4 / 9.6$$

$$= 5.28 \text{ s}$$

$$V_1 \times C_{A0} / F_{A0} = 5.28$$

Volume of first catalyst bed:

$$V_1 = (5.28 \times 0.215 \times 2883.76 \times 0.71) / (678.4)$$

$$= 3.375 \text{ m}^3$$

Volume of second catalyst bed:

$$V_2 = (5.28 \times 0.205 \times 0.9752 \times 2883.76) / (646.85)$$

$$= 4.695 \text{ m}^3$$

$$\text{Volume of first bed: } \quad \quad \quad \mathbf{3.375 \text{ m}^3}$$

$$\text{Volume of second bed: } \quad \quad \quad \mathbf{4.695 \text{ m}^3}$$

CO₂ Stripping Column

Liquid flow rate into stripping column = 266.578 mol/s Molecular

weight of liquid (15.3% MEA in H₂O) = 20.08

Equilibrium data

X	Y
0.001	0.003167
0.002	0.006347
0.05	0.17713
0.1	0.403061
0.15	0.701183
0.2	1.112676
0.25	1.717391
0.3	2.693182
0.35	4.532787
0.356	4.869114

For minimum steam rate from graph $Y_2 = 0.75 \frac{\text{kmol CO}_2}{\text{kmol steam}}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Minimum } G_s &= L_s(X_2 - X_1)/(Y_2 - Y_1) \\ &= 266.578 * (.356 - .001)/(1.1 - 0) \\ &= 86 \text{ mol steam/sec} \end{aligned}$$

for 1.5 times minimum, steam flow rate = 126.2 mole/sec therefore $Y_2 =$

1.1

also, $x_1 = 0.001$, $y_1 = 0$

$$x_2 = 0.356, y_2 = 1.1$$

we make a y-x plot to determine total number of stages which are found to be 4.8

Tower Diameter

$$\frac{L}{G} \sqrt{\frac{\rho_G}{\rho_L}} = 0.045$$

$$\therefore \alpha = 0.0744 * t + 0.01173$$

$$\beta = 0.0304 * t + 0.015$$

reference: Page 169 Mass transfer operations by R E Treybal

let $t = 0.75$ m

$$\therefore \alpha = 0.06753$$

$$\beta = 0.0378$$

$$\begin{aligned} C_F &= [0.06753 \log \frac{1}{0.556} + 0.0378] \left(\frac{0.04}{0.02} \right)^{0.2} \\ &= 0.1339 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} V_F &= C_F \left(\frac{\rho_L - \rho_G}{\rho_G} \right)^{0.5} \\ &= 4.1554 \text{ m/s} \end{aligned}$$

we use 80% of flooding velocity

$$\therefore V = 3.32 \text{ m/s}$$

$$\therefore A_n = Q/V = 2.33/3.32 = 0.7 \text{ m}^2$$

tray area used by one downspout = 8.8%

$$\therefore A_t = 0.7/(1-0.088)$$

$$= 0.7685 \text{ m}^2$$

$$\therefore D = 0.989 \text{ m}$$

Diameter = 1.00 m

height of tower = 5 * 0.75

$$= 3.75 \text{ m}$$

Hieght of tower = 3.75 + 2

$$= 5.75 \text{ m}$$

Process Utility

Feed Gas Compression

- Natural gas fuel heater
- Feed gas Compressor
- Start-up Compressor
- Natural gas knock-out drum

Reforming

- Process air saturator
- Primary Reformer
- Stem super heater
- Reactant preheater
- Combustion air heater
- Boiler
- Feed heater
- Process air heater
- First make gas boiler
- Second gas make boiler
- Make gas steam super heater
- Saturator DMW heater
- Saturator effluent cooler

- Flue gas fan
- Sulphur catch
- Secondary reformer
- Flue gas stack
- Steam drum
- Continuous blow down drum
- Intermittent blow down drum
- NOX reduction unit.

CO Shift

- Make gas BFW heater
- HT shift MG BFW heater
- HT shift steam super heater
- Naphtha Vaporiser
- Feed gas Heater
- Saturator circuit heater
- LP boiler
- HT shift converter
- LT shift converter.

CO₂ Removal:

- CO₂ absorber
- MEA regenerator
- Flash column
- MEA filter
- MEA make up filter
- Activated carbon filter
- Deaerator feed heater
- Lean MEA cooler
- Rich/lean exchanger
- Syngas trim cooler
- Semi-lean pump
- MEA make up pump
- MEA filter pump
- Condensate pump

- Process condensate pump
- Lean solution pump
- Semi rich solution pump
- Water make up pump
- Hydraulic turbine
- MEA solution storage tank

Methanation and Syngas Drying

- Methanator exchanger
- Methanator start-up heater
- Syngas cooler
- Adsorber regeneration heater
- Methanator
- Syngas adsorber

Ammonia Synthesis

- NH₃ converter start up heater
- NH₃ loop BFW heater
- NH₃ loop hot interchanger
- NH₃ loop cooler
- NH₃ loop cold interchanger
- NH₃ loop chillers
- Ammonia product heater
- Product ammonia pump
- Absorber bottoms pump
- NH₃ converter
- NH₃ converter cartridge
- NH₃ flash vessels
- LP NH₃ absorber

Purge Gas Treatment

- NH₃ absorber
- NH₃ still
- NH₃ absorber feed water cooler

- NH3 solution interchanger
- NH3 still condenser
- Purge gas H2 recovery unit

Synthesis Gas Compression

- Synthesis gas compressor
- NH3 loop circulator

Process Air Compression

- Process air compressor

Refrigeration

- Refrigeration condenser
- Refrigeration compressor
- Refrigeration receiver

Catalyst Used

1. Desulphurization

Supported cobalt-molybdenum (Comox) or nickel-molybdenum (Nimox) catalyst is used for hydrogenation of organic sulphur compounds in hydrocarbon feedstock to H₂S which is then removed.

H₂S is absorbed in a ZnO bed.

Temperature: 350-400 °C

Pressure: 40 Kg/cm²

Catalyst name: ZnO

Shape and size: Extruded rods or globules 3-5 mm dia.

Bulk density: 1.05-1.15 Kg/lit

Typical chemical composition (% by wt):

ZnO 95

R₂O₃ 5

Fe₂O₃ + Al₂O₃

Special features

- Low attrition loss.
- Gains strength in use.
- High H₂S absorption efficiency.

2. Primary reformer

Temperature: 700-800 oC
 Pressure: 30-40 Kg/cm₂
 Catalyst name: supported nickel catalyst
 Shape and size: Raschig rings (16×6×16 or 18×8×16 mm)
 Bulk density: .05-1.15 Kg/lit

Typical chemical composition (% by wt):

NiO 18
 CaO 18
 Al₂O₃ 74

Special features

- Highly pure and refractory.
- Al₂O₃ supports high activity and stability and long life

3. Secondary reformer

Temperature: 950 oC
 Pressure: 30-40 Kg/cm₂
 Catalyst name: supported nickel catalyst
 Bulk density: 1.1-1.2 Kg/lit
 Shape and size: Raschig rings (16×6×16 or 18×8×16 mm)

Typical chemical composition (% by wt):

NiO 12
 CaO 12
 Al₂O₃ 76

Special features

- High thermal shock resistance free of carry over problem
- High activity
- Excellent mechanical stability
- Long life

4. High temperature shift converter

Temperature: 340-450 oC

Pressure: 30-40 Kg/cm²

Catalyst name: iron – chromium catalyst

Shape and size: solid cylindrical tablets (6×6 or 10×6 or 10×10 mm)

Bulk density: 1.0-1.1 Kg/lit

Typical chemical composition (% by wt):

Fe₂O₃ 90

Cr₂O₃ 10

S0.015

Special features

- Extremely low Sulphur content with very low desulphurization time
- High and stable activity and strength

5. Low temperature shift converter

Temperature: 200-250 oC

Pressure: 30-40 Kg/cm²

Catalyst name: supported copper catalyst

Shape and size: solid cylindrical tablets (6×4 mm)

Bulk density: 1.25-1.3 Kg/lit

Typical chemical composition (% by wt):

CuO 25

ZnO 25

Al₂O₃ 35

Fe₂O₃ + TiO₂ 5

Special features

- High and stable activity and strength
- High resistance to poisons and steam condensation

6. Methanation

Temperature: 300-400 oC

Pressure: 30-40 Kg/cm²
Catalyst name: nickel supported on alumina catalyst
Shape and size: solid cylindrical tablets (6×4 mm)
Bulk density: 1.25-1.3 Kg/lit

Typical chemical composition (% by wt):

NiO 20
R₂O₃ 80

Special features

- Excellent thermal and mechanical stability
- High activity and long life.

7. Ammonia synthesis

Temperature: 400-500 oC
Pressure: upto 1000 atm
Catalyst name: doubly promoted iron catalyst
Shape and size: solid cylindrical tablets (1.5-12 mm)
Bulk density: 2.1-2.3 Kg/lit

Fe ₂ O ₃	91
Al ₂ O ₃	3
CaO	3
MgO	1
K ₂ O	1
SiO ₂	0.5

Special features

- Product of Indian magnetite with high activity and mechanical strength and stability

8. Catalyst poisoning

The active surface is sensitive to poisons.

Two classes of poisons are recognized: a) Permanent

b) Temporary

The permanent poison contains sulphur, phosphorus, arsenic, and chlorine and is represented by such compounds as H₂S and HCl. The temporary poisons contain oxygen and are represented by such compounds as CO, CO₂, O₂, and H₂O.

If exposure to temporary poisons does not last more than three to six days, the catalyst can usually be brought back to normal activity simply by exposing it to pure synthesis gas. In the presence of high concentration of hydrogen, the oxygenated compounds that make up the temporary poisons are converted to H₂O, which effectively blankets the active surfaces of the catalyst. Thus, temporary poisons are all about equivalent on an oxygen basis, with 100 ppm O₂ having same effect as 100 ppm CO₂ or 200 ppm H₂O or CO.

Plant Layout

The economic construction and operation of a process unit will depend on how well the plant equipment specified on the process flow sheet and laid out. The principal factors to be considered are:

1. Economic consideration: construction and operation cost.
2. The process requirement
3. Convenience of operation
4. Convenience of maintenance
5. Safety
6. Future expansion

Costs

The cost of construction can be minimized by adopting a layout that gives shortest run of connecting pipes between equipment, and adopting the least amount of structural steel work. However, this will not necessarily be the best arrangement for operation and maintenance.

Process Requirement

All the required equipment have to be placed properly within process. Even the installation of the auxiliaries should be done in such a way that it will occupy the least space.

Operation

Equipment that needs to have frequent operation should be located convenient to the control room. Valves, sample points, and instruments should be located at convenient position and height. Sufficient working space and headroom must be provided to allow easy access to equipment.

Maintenance

Heat exchangers need to be sited so that the tube bundles can be easily withdrawn for cleaning and tube

replacement. Vessels that require frequent replacement of catalyst or packing should be located on the outside of buildings. Equipment that requires dismantling for maintenance, such as compressors and large pumps, should be placed under cover.

Safety

Blast walls may be needed to isolate potentially hazardous equipment, and confine the effects of an explosion. At least two escape routes for operator must be provided from each level in the process building.

Plant Expansion

Equipment should be located so that it can be conveniently tied in with any future expansion of the process. Space should be left on pipe alleys for future needs, service pipes oversized to allow for future requirements.

Plant Layout

Main Sections

A complex chemical plant is divided into sections to limit the capital at risk, some of these areas should be located in areas where there is no fire risk. Care should be taken to give enough vacant space so as to avoid a chain reaction during the times of fire or any other emergencies.

Pipe Bridges

Equipments can be under pipe bridges but avoid large inventories of flammable materials or say pumps, moving liquids above atmospheric temperature. Enough bends should be given for the lines carrying hot liquids, otherwise thermal expansion may damage the lines.

Loading and Off-loading

Locate the loading and offloading facilities at the terminal parts of the plant so that regular traffic through the plant is minimized. Road tanker loading or offloading should be classified as danger areas and should be located at the periphery of the plant. These facilities should be so located that they are close to the railway terminal.

Plant Roads

Plant roads should give access to plants and should be arranged so that vehicles do not pass through process areas. Dead end roads should be avoided while access from any point to any part of the plant should be from two directions. Hazardous areas should not overlap the plant limits.

Administrative Block

This can be located at any place, but preferably at a place away from the plant. Normally it is kept at an enclosure slightly away from the production units. It should house the offices and rooms meant for conferences and emergency meetings. A refreshment room can also be provided in the building.

Plant Layout

Nomenclature of Various Places Shown in the above Plant Layout

1. **Administrative Block**
2. **Fire & Safety Department**
3. **Plant Utilities**
4. **Emergency Water**
5. **Packaging Plant**
6. **Process Plant**
7. **Expansion**
8. **Laboratory**
9. **Store**
10. **Stray Yard**
11. **Canteen**
12. **Storage Vessels**
13. **Workshops**

==== Connecting Roads

====

Conclusion

The process flow diagram shows that ammonia is a product whose manufacturing costs highly depends upon the availability and cost of the natural gases especially hydrogen. The heat in the plant is integrated through a network of heat exchangers so that minimum amount of steam is to be produced. The product quality depends on the maintenance of appropriate temperature & pressure conditions in the reactors. Various proportional, integral and derivative (PID) controllers in DDCS mode are used at different stages of the production of ammonia gas.

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